

Welding Engineering and Laser Processing Centre

Authors: Eloise Eimer & Jialuo Ding

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3269805

D1.1: Suitable new aluminium alloys for wire manufacturing Appendix 1: Literature review on WAAM

Project full title	Innovative Al filler Wires for Aircraft Structure
Project acronym	IAWAS
Topic / Call	JTI-CS2-2017-CfP07-AIR-01-34
Grant Agreement no.	821371
Start Date	02/10/2018
Duration	36 months
Version number	01.0
Due date	31/12/2018
Submission Date	02/01/2019

DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>

CHANGE CONTROL

Date	Version	Author (Company)	Changes to document
02/01/2019	v01.0	Cranfield University	Initial version

Literature review: WAAM and aluminium lithium alloys

INDEX

CHANGE CONTROL.....	2
INDEX	3
1. Wire + Arc Additive Manufacturing.....	5
1.1 Large parts manufacture	5
1.2 Material and processes.....	6
2. WAAM and aluminium	7
2.1 Porosity.....	7
2.1.1 Powder-based processes.....	7
2.1.2 WAAM.....	8
2.2 Solidification cracking	9
2.2.1 Powder bed processes.....	9
2.2.2 WAAM	11
2.3 Management of volatile elements.....	12
2.3.1 Powder bed process.....	12
2.3.2 WAAM	12
2.4 Alloy development.....	13
2.4.1 Powder bed processes.....	13
2.4.2 WAAM	13
3. WAAM and aluminium lithium	14
3.1 Process and deposition quality issues.....	14
3.1.1 Porosity.....	15
3.1.2 Solidification cracking	15
3.2 Material composition and mechanical properties.....	15

3.2.1 1420 Alloy family.....	16
3.2.2 Weldalite family.....	17
3.2.3 Effect of process parameters on WAAM material composition	17
3.2.4 Alloy developed for wrought product and WAAM	18
4. Alloy development strategies.....	19
5. Conclusion.....	21
Bibliography	21

No literature have been found on the use of aluminium lithium in Additive Manufacturing (AM) or Wire + Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM). Therefore, this literature review report focuses on what is WAAM, WAAM and aluminium alloys, and finally on WAAM and aluminium lithium alloys. This last sections is based on fusion welding and general literature

1. Wire + Arc Additive Manufacturing

Wire + Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) is a direct energy deposition process that uses an electric arc as the heat source and wire as raw material; it has the potential to build very large scale near-net-shape components [1]. Figure 1 shows a photograph taken during the plasma deposition of titanium and illustrates how the process works [2]. WAAM was first patented in 1925 [3] as a process intended to build ornamental items. Nowadays, this process is developed in order to manufacture end parts for diverse industrial applications. To build a component, a manipulator, a power source, and equipment such as torch and wire feeder, and a wire are required.

Figure 1 Plasma deposition of titanium [4]

1.1 Large parts manufacture

The possibility of building very large scale part relies on a high deposition rate and the size of the working area: it is possible to deposit up to 4 kg/h of Steel with WAAM, and even 10kg/h is achievable, but at the expense of the building precision [1]. Most materials do not require an extensive shielding and the local shielding provided by the torch is enough for specific materials such as Aluminium [5,6], and for more reactive materials a local shielding especially designed for WAAM can be used [7]. Therefore, the final part dimensions are limited only by the manipulator movement: a 6-meter long demonstrator aluminium part, shown in Figure 2 has been manufactured at Cranfield University to prove this potential.

Figure 2: Research team of the Welding Engineering and Laser Processing Centre carrying the largest AM metallic part [4]

WAAM process is not suitable for building very complex and small-scale shapes. The use of WAAM can be very beneficial to build near-net-shape large parts which are currently made by subtractive methods. Nowadays, to build a large component, a cast, extruded or rolled product of basic geometry is machined down to the final geometry: this generates a large amount of scrap which, even if it can be recycled, increases the total production cost. The buy-to-fly ratio, which is the ratio between the final part mass to the total material mass used to manufacture it, is often used to quantify the material waste generated during the manufacturing process. In subtractive manufacturing, it reaches values of 10 to 20 easily. WAAM has the possibility of manufacturing these same parts, but with a buy-to-fly ratio closer to 1. Figure 3 shows a part deposited with WAAM: currently machined from solid, the buy-to-fly ratio of this part is 12, and it could be reduced to 2.3 using WAAM [2].

Figure 3 Example of titanium near-net-shape WAAM part [2]

1.2 Material and processes

A wide range of material can be deposited with WAAM, including titanium [8–10], Inconel [11], steel [12,13], copper [14], magnesium [49], and various aluminium alloys[15–19]. Different heat sources can be used: Gas Metal Arc (GMA) is often preferred because the wire is coaxial to the torch in this process, and it facilitates the tool path planning[1]. Numerous studies in the literature focus on the

development of GMA based processes [5,6,20,21] or are based on the use of GMA processes [15,22–26]. Gas Tungsten Arc (GTA) [9,18,27,28] and plasma [8,13,24] can also be used.

2. WAAM and aluminium

Aluminium alloys are widely used in aerospace because of their high strength to density ratio, and this is one reason, among others, why many research projects have been carried out on the use of AM with aluminium alloys.

This section gives an overview of the challenges that AM has to tackle to produce aluminium parts and the current mechanical properties achieved in aluminium AM.

2.1 Porosity

A widespread issue in fusion welding of aluminium is porosity: this issue is also a major problem in AM. Hydrogen solubility in aluminium is much higher at liquid ($0.69 \text{ cm}^3/100\text{g}$) than solid state ($0.036 \text{ cm}^3/100\text{g}$) [29]. At liquid state, hydrogen from the atmosphere and wire and substrate surface contamination is dissolved into the melt pool. During solidification, the solubility of hydrogen drops and gas pores are formed: as aluminium solidify very quickly, most of these pores are trapped in the material.

2.1.1 Powder-based processes

Porosity in Powder Bed Fusion (PBF) is part of the broader problem of low-density material. For instance, Aboulkhair et al. studied the effect of process parameters on the porosity of AlSi10Mg parts and showed that porosity is drastically affected by parameters such as the scanning speed, the overlap between parallel layers and the laser power[30]. Figure 4 and Figure 5 illustrate the effect of the distance between passes on density and the scanning speed on the porosity level.

Figure 4: Illustration of the effect of scanning speed on the porosity level in an PBF part [30] <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>

However, these parameters affect the melt pool shape which can cause lack of fusion. In the latest study, the pockets of non-molten powder were removed during the grinding of the sample and the void then generated were counted as pores during the porosity analysis. This shows how difficult it is to study gas porosity in a material produced by a powder bed process. Similar studies all showed that it is challenging

to build high-density aluminium component using powder bed system and that the powder quality and process parameters have a drastic effect on the metal density [31,32].

Figure 5 Illustration of the effect of the hatch spacing (distance between parallel passes) on PFB material density [30] <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>

2.1.2 WAAM

Cong et al. showed the deposition process could play a key role in the porosity level: the use of low heat input and alternating current and voltage can drastically reduce the number of pores on 2319 alloy deposited with GMA processes[5]. Similar conclusion on the positive effect of alternating current was observed during the deposition of 5556 alloys with a GTA process [28]. However, no significant effect of alternating current was observed in Ryan et al. work on GMA deposition of 2319 alloy [25]. However, this latest work showed a high dependence between wire and deposition quality; the surface quality of the wire seems to play a critical role in the deposition quality, at least when a GMA process is used. The correlation between wire quality and porosity level in the deposit has also been observed during GMA deposition by Gu et al. and Pinter[24,33]. No extensive study has been published on the matter, but Pinter showed the use of AC plasma could drastically reduce the porosity level compared to GMA process, even for a poor wire quality.

Inter-pass rolling has been successfully applied to reduce the porosity level by Gu et al. in WAAM 2319 and 5087 alloys [23]. Figure 6 shows optical images of material as-deposited, rolled at different rolling load, and after heat treatment. The authors suggested that the porosity level was reduced due to the increase in dislocation density, well known for being a hydrogen trapping site.

Figure 6: Effect of inter-pass rolling and heat treatment on porosity level of 2319 deposited with a AC GMA process: optical images of the as-deposited (a), as heat treated (b), as rolled with a rolling load of 15, 30, and 45 kN (c), (d), and (e) and rolled with a rolling load of 45 then heat treated (f) material [23]

Many aluminium alloys require to be heat treated after being deposited to reach their highest mechanical properties. Unfortunately, the exposure to high temperature is detrimental to the porosity level in aluminium alloys [34] and this effect has been observed in WAAM material [23,35]. As illustrated in Figure 6, when inter-pass rolling is carried out, Gu et al. showed that the porosity level remains low, even after post-deposition heat treatment [23].

2.2 Solidification cracking

One of the main reasons why a limited number of aluminium alloys are available as raw material for AM, other than porosity, is their inappropriate solidification behaviour which makes them very sensitive towards hot cracking [36].

Most of the papers published on aluminium AM use Aluminium silicon alloys [18,19,26,33], or aluminium silicon magnesium alloys [30,32,37,38]: these two families, classified as 4000 and 6000 series respectively, they are widely used in casting and welding because most of their alloys have favourable solidification behaviour.

However, these alloys are not the most interesting ones in term of mechanical properties. For this reason, many studies focus on the solidification sensitivity of aluminium alloys, and how process parameters and alloy composition can be modified in order to make high strength aluminium alloys suitable for AM.

2.2.1 Powder bed processes

Mauduit et al. used aluminium powder of various alloys to check the compatibility between these alloys and PBF process. Un-surprisingly, samples made of 2017A, 2219, 7075, 7020, 6061 and 5083 alloys contained cracks. The authors also confirmed that the cracks were caused by the fast

solidification rate for 2017A and 7075 alloys [39]. Numerous hot cracks were also observed in 7075 PBF material manufactured by Kaufmann et al, and their attempt of reducing the number of these cracks by preheating the part to 200° C, in order to reduce the solidification rate, was not successful [40]. Aversa et al. and Martin et al. also used 7075 powder to manufacture samples with a laser powder bed machine: when using a commercially available powder, numerous cracks were observed in the material [41,42].

However, the authors of the two latest studies not only tried to manufacture samples using a generic powder; they also changed the chemical composition of this powder in order to deposit a modified crack-free aluminium zinc alloy. Aversa et al. mixed the 7075 powder with an AlSi10Mg powder to reduce the solidification range, in order to improve the fluidity of the melt pool and reduce the thermal expansion coefficient of the material. As shown in Figure 7, using a 50/50% mix made possible the production of a crack-free material. In this study, the material manufactured had a very different composition compared to the original alloy studied (7075): this had detrimental consequences on the final material properties [41].

Figure 7: Optical image of 7075 (a) and 50% 7075 - 50% AlSi10Mg (b) manufactured by a laser powder bed fusion process [41] (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Martin et al. realised a much more subtle change in composition: in their study, the 7075 powder was coated with 1 vol% hydrogen- stabilised zirconium nucleants using an electrostatic assembly technique. This addition of zirconium was made in order to add a high-density of Al₃ Zr nucleant phases in the material during solidification. These phases changed the solidification behaviour of the material: they prevented the formation of large columnar grains during the solidification and promoted the formation of small dendritic grains. This way, the authors manage to deposit crack-free, slightly modified 7075 alloys [42]. Figure 8 shows the tensile test results conducted in this study and illustrates the drastic improvement realised thanks to this small zirconium addition. Zhang et al. mixed pure zirconium powder to an aluminium copper magnesium powder and manufactured sample using SLM. Similar results than those obtained by Martin et al. were achieved: the addition of zirconium drastically reduces the crack sensitivity of the alloy [42].

Figure 8: Stress-strain curve obtained during the test of SLM material [42] (copyright 4585370910865)

2.2.2 WAAM

Few studies have been conducted on crack sensitive alloy and their suitability for WAAM processes. Fortunately, the solidification rate in WAAM is lower than in powder bed processes, and this reduces the likelihood of generating hot cracking during the solidification. If most of the studies on solidification cracking in PBF of aluminium alloys are focused on aluminium zinc alloys, the few studies conducted on solidification cracking in aluminium WAAM focus on aluminium magnesium alloy. Aluminium zinc alloys have not been investigated in WAAM mainly because of the behaviour of zinc in electric arcs and melt pools (see section 1.2.3.3).

Gu et al. used a tandem GMA system in order to deposit various composition of aluminium copper magnesium alloy by mixing two alloys among AlCu10, 2319, 5087 and 5554 [17]. Some compositions could not be successfully deposited without cracks, as illustrated in Figure 9. However, the authors showed that alloys containing between 4.2 to 6.3 %wt of copper and 0.8 to 1.5% of Mg could be deposited without any cracks visible during SEM imaging [17].

Figure 9 : Photograph of AlCuMg alloy deposited with WAAM: (a) Al-Cu3.71-Mg1.73 and (b) Al-Cu4.08-Mg1.62 [17]

Fixter et al. used a numerical model to predict hot crack susceptibility and showed that the 2024 alloy could be deposited by WAAM, despite being widely considered as un-weldable by fusion. There are no 2024 wires available on the market, and therefore a customised wire was made to confirm the results of the numerical model, and the authors were able to deposit crack-free 2024 alloy [43].

Qi et al. also managed to deposit 2024 alloy by WAAM using a GTA tandem system to mix 2319 with 5087 wires [44].

2.3 Management of volatile elements

High strength aluminium alloys have very complex compositions which include elements such as magnesium, zinc and lithium. Magnesium and zinc have a low boiling points, 1091°C and 907°C respectively, compared to aluminium melting and boiling points (660 °C and 2470°C). At liquid state, the temperature of the molten pool can be higher than these boiling points. Therefore, magnesium and zinc can vaporise during deposition, leading to a loss of these elements in the material after solidification.

2.3.1 Powder bed process

Martin et al. measured a zinc and magnesium loss of about 25 and 32% respectively during their manufacture of 7075+Zr by PBF [42], and Mauduit et al. measured a magnesium loss from 17 to 57% during the deposition of various aluminium alloys by PBF, and a zinc loss up to 33% during the manufacture of 7075 alloy [39]. This reduction in alloying elements will have a drastic impact on the mechanical properties of the material produced and will need to be counterbalanced, probably by adding more of these elements in the raw material. In addition, vaporisation of elements and its impact on melt pool behaviour has been investigated in fusion welding. This has not been addressed specifically in powder bed AM yet, but it is highly probable that the metal vapours impact on the process stability and the deposition quality.

2.3.2 WAAM

The reason why there are only a few studies on the deposition of aluminium zinc alloys is the very low boiling point of this element. In fusion welding, it has been demonstrated that it is challenging to use a filler wire which contains zinc: for instance, Woods described the droplet transfer in GMA with various aluminium wires. The author observed explosion inside metal droplets in the electric arc, and these explosions were more severe when the magnesium content of the wire was increased. The most unstable droplet transfer and almost systematic explosions were observed when a binary aluminium - zinc (5%) wire was used [45]. The use of aluminium zinc with a GMA process seems therefore impossible for welding and WAAM.

The vaporisation of magnesium has been observed by all studies focused on aluminium magnesium or aluminium copper magnesium alloys. Gu et al. measured a loss of about 1.2% during the GMA deposition of 5087 alloy (Wire Mg content of 5.05%) [16] and a loss up to 12% when depositing aluminium copper magnesium alloys using a GMA tandem system [17]. These values, considerably lower than those measured in powder bed studies, seems to be very sensitive to the deposition process: the heat input during the deposition of 5087 alloy (177.9 J/mm) was considerably lower than the heat input in the tandem study (up to 250 J/mm). In the latest study, the heat input varied with the different

wire feed speed used, and the authors noticed that the magnesium loss was higher when the heat input was increased. In their study, Brice et al. deposited 2139 and measured a magnesium loss up to 80%, but managed to counterbalance this loss by using a higher magnesium content in their wire [46].

2.4 Alloy development

Aluminium alloy compositions are designed to achieve the specific properties, such as tensile strength, toughness, and corrosion resistance, required by the final part specifications. However, the compositions are also dependent on the manufacturing process used: for instance, silicon is commonly added to cast alloys in order to improve fluidity and their solidification behaviour. It is therefore natural to think that most wrought aluminium alloys are not adapted to AM processes.

2.4.1 Powder bed processes

A few selections of powder are available on the market: to deposit a new alloy, it is possible to manufacture a customised powder, but this takes time and is expensive. An obvious route of new powder development is to mix powder of different alloy in order to produce powders of various compositions. This route has been chosen in various studies [41,47–49], but it is not always easy to produce a good quality powder. Commercialised powders have all different characteristic and mixing powders of un-even particle size or flowability can be an issue.

Martin et al. used another approach by coating their powder with 1 vol% hydrogen stabilised zirconium nucleants [42]

2.4.2 WAAM

As for powders, the manufacture of customised wire composition is very time and money consuming, and not all composition can be drawn. In order to produce a various range of compositions, it is required to use existing wires. Pickin et al. show the possibility of using a tandem system with aluminium magnesium and aluminium copper wires to produce a weld with a customised composition. Even a third wire was used to feed copper into the melt pool away from the arc [50,51].

In 2018, Gu et al. used the same strategy to deposit aluminium copper magnesium by WAAM [25] with a tandem GMA process. In parallel, Qi et al. deposited aluminium copper magnesium alloys with a double wire GTA system, shown in Figure 10 [52]. None of this studies includes the deposition of aluminium zinc alloys.

Figure 10: Double GMA system developed and used by Qi et al. to deposit aluminium copper magnesium alloys [44] (copyright 4622571449704)

3. WAAM and aluminium lithium

Little data can be found in the literature on the use of aluminium lithium in AM processes. This is due to the lithium. Heard focused his PhD thesis on aluminium lithium-free form fabrication [53]: the author shows the effect of processes (WAAM-CMT, Laser re-melting, and Electrospark Deposition) on solidification rate, lithium depletion and segregation, and mechanical properties. The solidification rate was too low in WAAM, and large segregation of alloying elements was observed. Therefore, without solution treatment, the properties of the as-deposited material remained low. Also, some lithium enrichment was observed on the specimen surface: this could be a drastic issue during the deposition of near-net-shape components.

The lack of literature on aluminium lithium AM can be attributed to the relative novelty of AM processes, but also due to the absence of raw material supplier, and to the potential challenges lithium could bring such as porosity, lithium loss, and cracking. However, for the IAWAS project, the two fields of aluminium lithium fusion welding and aluminium lithium manufacture, microstructures and mechanical properties should be included in the literature review.

The literature on fusion welding of aluminium lithium can be used to assess the challenges in term of deposition quality: issues such as porosity and hot cracking will occur similarly than in fusion welding. This is detailed in the next section 3.1.

Aluminium lithium alloys have been manufactured since the 1920s, and their composition, microstructures, and properties are continuously investigated. In order to develop new alloys adapted to WAAM, a general literature review on aluminium lithium should be conducted. This is the focus of section 3.2.

3.1 Process and deposition quality issues

An extensive literature review on aluminium lithium welding should be conducted for the IAWAS project for the welding part of the study. The following section purpose is not to give an extensive review on welding but to focus on the link between aluminium lithium welding and AM.

3.1.1 Porosity

During WAAM and welding, two types of porosity can occur: inter-dendritic and bulk porosity. The first one comes from the formation of voids at the end of the solidification process where gas is trapped in between dendrites, and the second results from supersaturation of gas in the melt pool. Due to the low vaporisation point of lithium and its high reactivity with oxygen, lithium can generate instabilities during the deposition process leading to a high level of porosity [54, p.260].

During WAAM, the material undergoes numerous re-melting and reheating cycles. These cycles can cause an increase in alloying element segregation and inter-dendritic pore size and number. For WAAM and powder bed processes, section 2.1 shows that process parameters play a key role in the porosity level. Welding parameters also influence the porosity level in aluminium lithium welding. So far, no study has been reported on the Laser + Arc system which will be used for the deposition of aluminium lithium.

During the manufacture of the demonstrator at the end of the IAWAS project, the substrate will be, in all likelihood, included in the design. This means that pores will be formed in two different zones: at the interface between the substrate and WAAM material and in the deposited material. Little is known about the porosity level in the deposited material, but literature in welding shows how to reduce the porosity at the interface between the substrate and deposited material. During welding, the preparation of the substrate [55] can play a key role in reducing porosity as well as the use of a shielding gas [54, p.263]. Extensive literature research should be conducted on this issue by the partner focusing on the laser welding side of the project.

The material composition can also have an impact on porosity by changing the solidification behaviour, and generate more or less inter-dendritic voids, and by changing the hydrogen solubility in the matrix [54, p.263].

3.1.2 Solidification cracking

Solidification behaviour and mechanical constraints around the melt pool are the two causes of hot cracking in aluminium welding [54, chap.9,56]. During WAAM, mechanical constraints around the melt pool are much lower than during welding due to the change in geometry. This means that the tendency of hot cracking is lower in WAAM: for instance, alloys such as 2024, widely considered as unweldable, can be deposited using WAAM [17,43,57].

Regarding the solidification behavior, some aluminium alloys have been especially designed to be welded. This is the case of the 01420 (and other alloy of this family) and weldalite (2195) family.

3.2 Material composition and mechanical properties

- Iron and silicon are damaging impurities for Al Li alloys: these should be avoided in both substrate and wire to prevent hot cracking.

- Zirconium is widely used as a grain refiner but can lead to specific elongated pancake shape grains in the case of aluminium alloys especially when a large quantity is used (up to 0.7% in 2099 alloy). It also lead to strong texture, delamination, precipitates free-zone that generate drastic anisotropic properties. Zirconium can be replaced by combinations of Mn, Sc, and Ag. [54, chap.1]

Two families could be investigated with WAAM: Al-Li-Mg (such as 01420) and Al-Li-Cu-Mg (such as AA2195)

3.2.1 1420 Alloy family

The 01420 alloy was developed by the USSR in the 1960s. It has a very low density of 2.47 g/cm³, which is 10 to 12 % less than 2024 alloy. Its composition is given in Table 1 along with the compositions of alloy developed based on 01420.

It is a weldable alloy (GTA welding with a AlMg6 filler wire [58]):

- Join efficiency up to 70% of the base plate in as welded condition
- Join efficiency up to 99.6% achieved after solution treatment (with air cooling) and aging

Table 1: Chemical composition of 01420 alloy family.

Alloy	Li	Cu	Mg	Zr	Others
1420	2.1	-	5.0	0.1	0.5 Mn
1421	2.1	-	5.1	-	0.17 Sc
1423	1.9	-	3.5	0.1	0.08 Sc
1424	1.7	-	5.35	-	0.1 Zn 0.08 Ag 0.08 Sc

The 1424 alloy is a third generation alloy and was developed in 1999. It could replace 2024 alloy in aircrafts structures: it is weldable and has a lower density and a higher elasticity modulus than 2014 [59]. This alloy can be air hardened to achieve medium strength (UTS = 477–490 MPa, YS = 360–375 MPa, and $\delta = 8\text{--}10\%$) and a high thermal stability of fracture toughness and crack resistance properties [60].

- More references:
 - Prasad NE., Gokhale AA., Wanhill RJH. Aluminum-Lithium Alloys : Processing, Properties, and Applications. 596 p. [54]
 - Fridlyander IN., Shiryayeva N V., Malinkina TI., F. AI., Gorokhova TA. Properties of welded joints in alloy 01420. *Metatlovedenie i Termicheskaya Obrabotka Metallov*. 1975; 3: 53–54. [58]
 - Pickens JR., Langan TJ., Barta E. Weldability of Al 5Mg 2Li 0.1 Zr alloy 01420.pdf. *Aluminium lithium alloys III*. Oxford: The institue of metals; 1985. pp. 137–147. [55]

- Fridlyander IN., Khokhlatova LB., Kolobnev NI., Rendiks K., Tempus G. THERMALLY STABLE ALUMINUM-LITHIUM ALLOY 1424 FOR APPLICATION IN WELDED FUSELAGE. Metal Science and Heat Treatment. 2002; 44. [59]

Recommendation

These Al Mg Li alloys seem to be of interest as they could achieve high mechanical properties even in as-deposited condition: if the demonstrator includes the substrate, it would be very beneficial to not carry out heat treatment

3.2.2 Weldalite family

Weldalite alloys are Al-Cu-Li + minor addition of Mg, Ag and Zr. Plastic deformation is not required to achieve high strength, and these alloys were developed to be welded and have therefore a low sensitivity towards hot cracking. The first alloy of this family, weldalite 049 ([Al-(4.5-6.3)Cu-1.3Li-0.4Ag-0.4Mg-0.14Zr]) led to the development of numerous alloys such as These alloys could be interesting for WAAM as they have a favorable solidification path [54]

More references:

- Marinkovich JM., Mohamed FA., Pickens JR., Lavernia EJ. The Spray Atomization and Deposition of Weldalite 049. JOM. 1989; 49(9): 36–41. [61]
- Kostrivas A., Lippold JC. Weldability of Li-bearing aluminium alloys. International Materials Reviews. 1999; 44(6): 217–237. [62]
- Brotzu A., Felli F., Pilone D. Investigation on some factors affecting crack formation in high resistance aluminum alloys. Frattura ed Integrità Strutturale. 2017; 11(42): 272–279. Available at: DOI:10.3221/IGF-ESIS.42.29 [63]
- Murayama M., Hono K. Role of Ag and Mg on precipitation of T1 phase in an Al-Cu-Li-Mg-Ag alloy. Scripta Materialia. 2001; 44(4): 701–706. Available at: DOI:10.1016/S1359-6462(00)00651-5 [64]
- Pickens JR. Review Recent developments in the weldability of lithium-containing aluminium alloys. Journal of materials science. 1990; 25: 3035–3047. [65]

3.2.3 Effect of process parameters on WAAM material composition

Lithium depletion is a common issue during the casting and welding of aluminium lithium alloys [54, chaps 6 & 9]. Figure 11 shows the lithium concentration across a weld made using a GTAW (Gas Tungsten Arc Welding) process on a 01420 substrate, with a 01420 wire filler. The weld was made of three passes: the bottom of the weld is therefore reheated twice, while the top of the weld is in as-welded condition. The top of the weld (the crop) has a concentration 2.5 times higher than the

bottom of the weld (the root). The authors believed this was due to the high volatility of lithium at high temperature.

Recommendations

During WAAM, the material will undergo numerous heat cycles: this could lead to a drastic lithium depletion. To reduce lithium loss, specific shielding conditions could be used, as well as adapted deposition parameters. A significant amount of time should be allocated to the study of the effect of process parameters on lithium depletion (phase 1 of WP3). To investigate lithium depletion, it will probably be required to use technique which enable local chemical composition measurement.

Figure 11: Peak height ratios for Li and U, normalized to Al, from the root to the crop of a three passes GTAW weld of a 01420 substrate with 01420 filler wire [55]

3.2.4 Alloy developed for wrought product and WAAM

It is important to note that aluminium alloys were developed for wrought products, and what has been learned over the years was based on the performance of these wrought products. Issues such

as corrosion, stress corrosion and anisotropy can be caused by specific texture, grain shape and composition at grain boundaries. These highly depend on the manufacturing process, and could be different for the material deposited with WAAM.

4. Alloy development strategies

IAWAS aims at developing a new alloy for WAAM. In order to develop new compositions, two strategies can be implemented.

The first one consist in manufacturing new wires with customised composition, and try them: this method is illustrated in Figure 12. The experimental results provide information on the effect of the specific composition used on the material microstructure and properties, but does not enable a full understanding of the effect of each alloying elements on the melt-pool dynamic, solidification behaviour, microstructure, and mechanical properties. Also, this method is very costly and time consuming: for each iteration, a new alloy needs to be casted, extruded and drawn.

Another method, used in Cranfield University and other research institution, consist in using a mix of two or three wires [17,44,66,67]. With this technique, it is possible to adjust the composition of the deposited material by changing the wire feed speed of the different wires. This technique is more time and cost effective as it is possible to deposit different composition with at least two wire. This technique also makes possible to investigate the effect of alloying element in a systematic way.

Figure 12: Development of WAAM alloy – first strategy

All the studies focused on alloy development with two or three wires used a GTA or GMA systems. Lithium is likely to generate a high porosity level in the deposited material due to its low vaporisation point; vaporisation could also reduce the lithium concentration in the material. The lithium high

diffusivity and tendency to oxidize will probably be an issue as well, as it might lead to lithium depletion at liquid stage and at high temperature.

In order to reduce the likelihood of lithium loss, innovative processes such as Plasma Transfer Arc (PTA) or Gas Metal Arc (GMA) combined with laser should be used. The wire with a lithium content will be fed as a cold wire directly in the melt pool to avoid lithium vaporisation in the electric arc. Figure 13 shows a very similar set up which has been used previously to work on aluminium alloy development for WAAM applications. Figure 14 shows a diagram of the GMA + laser process, with feeding of the aluminium lithium wire in the melt pool and away from the electric arc.

Figure 13: Previous experimental set up used for aluminium alloys development

Figure 14: Diagram of the Laser + GMA set up with cold aluminium lithium wire feeding

5. Conclusion

- Previous studies on WAAM showed that process parameters have a great impact on deposition quality, especially porosity as well as wire quality. Inter-pass rolling can be used to reduce drastically the porosity level in WAAM material.
- Wire composition has a huge impact on solidification behaviour and sensitivity towards hot cracking. However, sensitivity toward hot cracking is not as critical for WAAM as for welding because of the lower constrain around the melt pool in AM.
- Several studies used a strategy to develop new aluminium alloys for WAAM by using tandem systems and mixing different alloys to successfully deposit a wide range of chemical compositions. Aluminium copper magnesium and aluminium zinc alloys have been deposited.
- Al-Mg-Li as well as Al-Cu-Li alloys could be a good options for aluminium lithium alloys for WAAM development. Regarding corrosion resistance and mechanical property anisotropy issues, it is difficult to predict the behaviour of WAAM material as it will have a complete different microstructure to wrought material.

Bibliography

1. Williams SW., Martina F., Addison AC., Ding J., Pardal G., Colegrove P. Wire+Arc Additive Manufacturing. *Materials Science and Technology*. 2016; 32(7): 641–647. Available at: DOI:10.1179/1743284715Y.0000000073
2. Wire + Arc Additive Manufacturing — WAAMMat. Available at: <https://waammat.com/about/waam> (Accessed: 18 September 2018)
3. Baker R. Method of making decorative articles. United States Patent Office. United states; 1925. Report No.: 1,533,300.
4. Welding Engineering and Laser Processing Center. Application and business. Available at: <https://waammat.com/about/business-drivers> (Accessed: 18 September 2018)
5. Cong B., Ding J., Williams SW. Effect of arc mode in cold metal transfer process on porosity of additively manufactured Al-6.3%Cu alloy. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*. 2014; 76(9–12): 1593–1606. Available at: DOI:10.1007/s00170-014-6346-x
6. Ayarkwa KF., Williams S., Ding J. Investigation of pulse advance cold metal transfer on aluminium wire arc additive manufacturing. *Int. J. Rapid Manufacturing*. 2015; 5(1): 44–57.
7. Ding J., Colegrove P., Martina F., Williams S., Wiktorowicz R., Palt MR. Development of a laminar flow local shielding device for wire+arc additive manufacture. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. Elsevier B.V.; 2015; 226: 99–105. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2015.07.005
8. Martina F., Mehnen J., Williams SW., Colegrove P., Wang F. Investigation of the benefits of plasma deposition for the additive layer manufacture of Ti-6Al-4V. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. Elsevier B.V.; 2012; 212(6): 1377–1386. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2012.02.002

9. Wang F., Williams S., Colegrove P., Antonysamy AA. Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of Wire and Arc Additive Manufactured Ti-6Al-4V. *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*. 2013; 44(2): 968–977. Available at: DOI:10.1007/s11661-012-1444-6
10. Brandl E., Palm F., Michailov V., Viehweger B., Leyens C. Mechanical properties of additive manufactured titanium (Ti-6Al-4V) blocks deposited by a solid-state laser and wire. *Materials and Design*. Elsevier Ltd; 2011; 32(10): 4665–4675. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.matdes.2011.06.062
11. Baufeld B. Mechanical Properties of INCONEL 718 Parts Manufactured by Shaped Metal Deposition (SMD). *Journal of materials engin.* 2012; 21(July): 1416–1421. Available at: DOI:10.1007/s11665-011-0009-y
12. Queguineur A., Rückert G., Cortial F., Hascoët JY. Evaluation of wire arc additive manufacturing for large-sized components in naval applications. *Welding in the World*. *Welding in the World*; 2018; 62(2): 259–266. Available at: DOI:10.1007/s40194-017-0536-8
13. Xu X., Ganguly S., Ding J., Guo S., Williams S., Martina F. Microstructural evolution and mechanical properties of maraging steel produced by wire + arc additive manufacture process. *Materials Characterization*. Elsevier; 2018; 143(September): 152–162. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.matchar.2017.12.002
14. Dong B., Pan Z., Shen C., Ma Y., Li H. Fabrication of Copper-Rich Cu-Al Alloy Using the Wire-Arc Additive Manufacturing Process. *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions B: Process Metallurgy and Materials Processing Science*. Springer US; 2017; 48(6): 3143–3151. Available at: DOI:10.1007/s11663-017-1071-0
15. Gu J., Ding J., Williams SW., Gu H., Bai J., Zhai Y., et al. The strengthening effect of inter-layer cold working and post-deposition heat treatment on the additively manufactured Al– 6.3Cu alloy. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. Elsevier; 2016; 230: 26–34. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2015.11.006
16. Gu J., Wang X., Bai J., Ding J., Williams S., Zhai Y., et al. Deformation microstructures and strengthening mechanisms for the wire+arc additively manufactured Al-Mg4.5Mn alloy with inter-layer rolling. *Materials Science and Engineering A*. Elsevier B.V.; 2018; 712(November 2017): 292–301. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.msea.2017.11.113
17. Gu J., Bai J., Ding J., Williams S., Wang L., Liu K. Design and cracking susceptibility of additively manufactured Al-Cu-Mg alloys with tandem wires and pulsed arc. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. Elsevier; 2018; 262(May): 210–220. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2018.06.030
18. Wang H., Jiang W., Ouyang J., Kovacevic R. Rapid prototyping of 4043 Al-alloy parts by VP-GTAW. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. 2004; 148(1): 93–102. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2004.01.058
19. Gomez Ortega A., Corona Galvan L., Deschaux-Beaume F., Mezrag B., Rouquette S. Effect of process parameters on the quality of aluminium alloy Al5Si deposits in wire and arc additive manufacturing using a cold metal transfer process. *Science and Technology of Welding and Joining*. 2018; 23(4): 316–332. Available at: DOI:10.1080/13621718.2017.1388995
20. Ding D., Pan Z., Cuiuri D., Li H. A multi-bead overlapping model for robotic wire and arc additive manufacturing (WAAM). *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*. Elsevier; 2015; 31: 101–110. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.rcim.2014.08.008
21. Zhang C., Li Y., Gao M., Zeng X. Wire arc additive manufacturing of Al-6Mg alloy using variable polarity cold metal transfer arc as power source. *Materials Science and Engineering*

- A. 2018; 711(August 2017): 415–423. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.msea.2017.11.084
22. Cong B., Qi Z., Qi B., Sun H., Zhao G., Ding J. A Comparative Study of Additively Manufactured Thin Wall and Block Structure with Al-6.3%Cu Alloy Using Cold Metal Transfer Process. *Applied science*. 2017; 7: 1–11. Available at: DOI:10.3390/app7030275
 23. Gu J., Ding J., Williams SW., Gu H., Ma P., Zhai Y. The effect of inter-layer cold working and post-deposition heat treatment on porosity in additively manufactured aluminum alloys. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. 2016; 230: 26–34. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2015.11.006
 24. Pinter Z. Study of wire +arc additive manufacturing. Cranfield University; 2017.
 25. Ryan EM., Sabin TJ., Watts JF., Whiting MJ. The influence of build parameters and wire batch on porosity of wire and arc additive manufactured aluminium alloy 2319. *Journal of Materials Processing Tech. Elsevier*; 2018; 262(July): 577–584. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2018.07.030
 26. Haselhuhn AS., Buhr MW., Wijnen B., Sanders PG., Pearce JM. Structure-property relationships of common aluminum weld alloys utilized as feedstock for GMAW-based 3-D metal printing. *Materials Science and Engineering A*. 2016; 673: 511–523. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.msea.2016.07.099
 27. Bai JY., Yang CL., Lin SB., Dong BL., Fan CL. Mechanical properties of 2219-Al components produced by additive manufacturing with TIG. *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol*. 2015; 86(1–4): 479–485. Available at: DOI:10.1007/s00170-015-8168-x
 28. Ayarkwa KF., Williams SW., Ding J. Assessing the effect of TIG alternating current time cycle on aluminium wire + arc additive manufacture. *Additive Manufacturing. Elsevier B.V.*; 2017; 18: 186–193. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.addma.2017.10.005
 29. Courbiere M. Welding Aluminum Alloys. In: Blondeau R (ed.) *Metallurgy and Mechanics of Welding: Processes and Industrial Applications*. London: ISTE; 2008. pp. 433–471. Available at: DOI:10.1002/9780470611272.ch13
 30. Aboulkhair NT., Everitt NM., Ashcroft I., Tuck C. Reducing porosity in AlSi10Mg parts processed by selective laser melting. *Additive Manufacturing. Elsevier B.V.*; 2014; 1–4: 77–86. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.addma.2014.08.001
 31. Louvis E., Fox P., Sutcliffe CJ. Selective laser melting of aluminium components. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology. Elsevier B.V.*; 2011; 211(2): 275–284. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2010.09.019
 32. Olakanmi EO. Selective laser sintering / melting (SLS / SLM) of pure Al , Al – Mg , and Al – Si powders : Effect of processing conditions and powder properties. *Journal of Materials Processing Tech. Elsevier B.V.*; 2013; 213(8): 1387–1405. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2013.03.009
 33. Gu J., Ding J., Cong B., Bai J., Gu H., Williams SW., et al. The Influence of Wire Properties on the Quality and Performance of Wire+Arc Additive Manufactured Aluminium Parts. *Advanced Materials Research*. 2014; 1081: 210–214. Available at: DOI:10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.1081.210
 34. Toda H., Hidaka T., Kobayashi M., Uesugi K., Takeuchi A., Horikawa K. Growth behavior of hydrogen micropores in aluminum alloys during high-temperature exposure. *Acta Materialia. Acta Materialia Inc.*; 2009; 57: 2277–2290. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.actamat.2009.01.026
 35. Bai J., Ding HL., Gu JL., Wang XS., Qiu H. Porosity evolution in additively manufactured

- aluminium alloy during high temperature exposure. 1st International conference on New Material and Chemical Industry. 2017. pp. 1–4. Available at: DOI:10.1088/1742-6596/365/1/011001
36. Kou S. Weld Metal Solidification Cracking. *Welding metallurgy*, second edition. John Wiley & Sons; 2003. pp. 263–300.
 37. Brandl E., Heckenberger U., Holzinger V., Buchbinder D. Additive manufactured AlSi10Mg samples using Selective Laser Melting (SLM): Microstructure, high cycle fatigue, and fracture behavior. *Materials & Design*. Elsevier Ltd; 2012; 34: 159–169. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.matdes.2011.07.067
 38. Kempen K., Thijs L., Van Humbeeck J., Kruth J-P. Mechanical Properties of AlSi10Mg Produced by Selective Laser Melting. *Physics Procedia*. 2012; 39: 439–446. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.phpro.2012.10.059
 39. Mauduit A., Pillot S., Gransac H. Study of the suitability of aluminum alloys for additive manufacturing by laser powder bed fusion. *UPB Scientific Bulletin, Series B: Chemistry and Materials Science*. 2017; 79(4): 219–238.
 40. Kaufmann N., Imran M., Wischeropp TM., Emmelmann C., Siddique S., Walther F. Influence of process parameters on the quality of aluminium alloy EN AW 7075 using selective laser melting (SLM). *Physics Procedia*. 2016; 83: 918–926. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.phpro.2016.08.096
 41. Aversa A., Marchese G., Manfredi D., Lorusso M., Calignano F., Biamino S., et al. Laser Powder Bed Fusion of a High Strength Al-Si-Zn-Cu Alloy. *Metals*. 2018; : 1–12. Available at: DOI:10.3390/met8050300
 42. Martin JH., Yahata BD., Hundley JM., Mayer JA., Schaedler TA., Pollock TM. 3D printing of high-strength aluminium alloys. *Nature*. 2017; 549(7672): 365–369. Available at: DOI:10.1038/nature23894
 43. Fixter J., Gu J., Ding J., Williams SW., Prangnell PB. Preliminary Investigation into the Suitability of 2xxx Alloys for Wire-Arc Additive Manufacturing. *Mater. Sci. Forum*. Scientific.net; 2017. pp. 611–616. Available at: DOI:10.4028/www.scientific.net/MSF.877.611
 44. Qi Z., Cong B., Qi B., Sun H., Zhao G., Ding J. Microstructure and mechanical properties of double wire + arc additively manufactured Al Cu Mg alloys. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. Elsevier; 2018; 255(August 2017): 347–353. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2017.12.019
 45. Woods RA. Metal Transfer in Aluminum Alloys. *Welding Research supplement*. 1979; February: 59–66.
 46. Brice C., Shenoy R., Kral M., Buchannan K. Precipitation behavior of aluminum alloy 2139 fabricated using additive manufacturing. *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*. Elsevier; 2015; 648: 9–14. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.msea.2015.08.088
 47. Zhang H., Zhu H., Nie X., Yin J., Hu Z., Zeng X. Effect of Zirconium addition on crack, microstructure and mechanical behavior of selective laser melted Al-Cu-Mg alloy. *Scripta Materialia*. Acta Materialia Inc.; 2017; 134: 6–10. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.scriptamat.2017.02.036
 48. Roberts CE., Bourell D., Watt T., Cohen J. A novel processing approach for additive manufacturing of commercial aluminium alloys. *Physics Procedia*. 2016; 83: 909–917. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.phpro.2016.08.095

49. Bartkowiak K., Ullrich S., Frick T., Schmidt M. New Developments of Laser Processing Aluminium alloys via additive manufacturing technique.pdf. *Physics Procedia*. 2011; 12: 393–401.
50. Rao KS., Reddy GM., Rao KP. Studies on partially melted zone in aluminium-copper alloy welds - Effect of techniques and prior thermal temper. *Materials Science and Engineering A*. 2005; 403(1–2): 69–76. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.msea.2005.04.041
51. Malarvizhi S., Balasubramanian V. Effect of welding processes on AA2219 aluminium alloy joint properties. *Transactions of Nonferrous Metals Society of China*. 2011; 21(5): 962–973. Available at: DOI:10.1016/S1003-6326(11)60808-X
52. Katgerman L., Eskin D. Hardening, Annealing, and Aging. In: Totten GE, MacKenzie DS (eds.) *Handbook of aluminum Volume 1 Physical Metallurgy and Processes*. CRC Press; 2003. pp. 259–304.
53. Heard DW. *Rapid Solidification of an Aluminum-Lithium Alloy for Solid Freeform Fabrication Applications*. PhD. McGill University, Montreal; 2013.
54. Prasad NE., Gokhale AA., Wanhill RJH. *Aluminum-Lithium Alloys : Processing, Properties, and Applications*. 596 p.
55. Pickens JR., Langan TJ., Barta E. Weldability of Al 5Mg 2Li 0.1 Zr alloy 01420.pdf. *Aluminium lithium alloys III*. Oxford: The institute of metals; 1985. pp. 137–147.
56. Cao G., Kou S. Predicting and Reducing Liquation-Cracking Susceptibility Based on Temperature vs. Fraction Solid. *Welding Journal*. 2006; 85(Jan): 9–18.
57. Qi Z., Cong B., Qi B., Ding J. Properties of wire + arc additively manufactured 2024 aluminum alloy with different solution treatment temperature. *Materials letters*. 2018; 230: 275–278. Available at: DOI:10.1016/j.matlet.2018.07.144
58. Fridlyander IN., Shiryayeva N V., Malinkina TI., F. AI., Gorokhova TA. Properties of welded joints in alloy 01420. *Metatlovedenie i Termicheskaya Obrabotka Metallov*. 1975; 3: 53–54.
59. Fridlyander IN., Khokhlatova LB., Kolobnev NI., Rendiks K., Tempus G. THERMALLY STABLE ALUMINUM-LITHIUM ALLOY 1424 FOR APPLICATION IN WELDED FUSELAGE. *Metal Science and Heat Treatment*. 2002; 44.
60. Khokhlatova LB., Kolobnev NI., Oglodkov MS., Mikhaylov ED. ALUMINUM-LITHIUM ALLOYS FOR AIRCRAFT BUILDING. *Metallurgist*. 2012; 56(5): 31–35.
61. Marinkovich JM., Mohamed FA., Pickens JR., Lavernia EJ. The Spray Atomization and Deposition of Weldalite 049. *JOM*. 1989; 49(9): 36–41.
62. Kostivas A., Lippold JC. Weldability of Li-bearing aluminium alloys. *International Materials Reviews*. 1999; 44(6): 217–237.
63. Brotzu A., Felli F., Pilone D. Investigation on some factors affecting crack formation in high resistance aluminum alloys. *Frattura ed Integrità Strutturale*. 2017; 11(42): 272–279. Available at: DOI:10.3221/IGF-ESIS.42.29
64. Murayama M., Hono K. Role of Ag and Mg on precipitation of T1 phase in an Al-Cu-Li-Mg-Ag alloy. *Scripta Materialia*. 2001; 44(4): 701–706. Available at: DOI:10.1016/S1359-6462(00)00651-5
65. Pickens JR. Review Recent developments in the weldability of lithium-containing aluminium alloys. *Journal of materials science*. 1990; 25: 3035–3047.

66. Pickin CG., Williams SW., Prangnell PB., Robson J., Lunt M. Control of weld composition when welding high strength aluminium alloy using the tandem process. *Science and Technology of Welding and Joining*. 2009; 14(8): 734–739. Available at: DOI:10.1179/136217109X12505932584817
67. Pickin CG., Williams SW., Prangnell P., Derry C., Lunt M. Control of weld composition when arc welding high strength aluminium alloys using multiple filler wires. *Science and Technology of Welding and Joining*. 2010; 15(6): 491–496. Available at: DOI:10.1179/136217110X12785889549660